

Attitudinal And Behavioural Patterns Towards Malaria Attack And Treatment among The Selected People In Irun-Akoko, Ondo State Nigeria

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Abstract

The negative impacts of malaria attack remain a major public health issue in the world which is commonly transmitted through a bite from an infected female Anopheles mosquito. However, the attitudes, perceptions and behaviours of people towards malaria attack and treatment in the rural communities still remain a serious challenge especially in the developing countries such as Nigeria. The general objective was to examine the attitudes and behavioural patterns towards malaria attack and treatment among rural community dwellers in Irun-Akoko North West, Ondo state. Survey research was conducted among the selected rural community dwellers to elicit information about the burden of malaria in the study area. It was a cross-sectional descriptive study. From the analysis of the study, about 48.7% of the respondents believed that malaria incidence is very serious in their areas. Majority (78.1%) believed that malaria is deadly if it is not treated on time. Meanwhile, from the period of a week ago to over a year, majority (73.0%) of the respondents mentioned they have experienced sickness (malaria). About 43.8% experienced the symptoms less than a week before adequate treatment was sought. Medical treatment (drugs and injection) and self-medication (herbal medicine and drugs at chemist) with 46.9% and 41.9% are the major treatment methods adopted respectively. Majority (74.4%) recovered from malaria sickness at their first treatment. It is evident that the belief-systems and attitudes of people about malaria attack are crucial factors in determining their health-related behaviours and health-seeking behaviour.

Keywords: Malaria attack, Beliefs, Perception, Malaria Prevention, Rural Dwellers